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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP3 – Consumer engagement methodology definition and activity coordination

D3.4 – Living Lab activities plan and evaluation report v4

Responsible organisation	SIN
Contributing organisation(s)	UCC
Due date of Deliverable	31/12/2024
Actual date of submission	23/12/2024
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Disclaimer: ACCEPT is a project co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 - Call: H2020-SC3-2018-2020 EC-3 Consumer engagement and demand response Programme under Grant Agreement No. 957781. The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Communities. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use, which may be made, of the information contained therein.

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Deliverable is

Fully Accepted	✓
Accepted with minor revisions	
Rejected unless modified as suggested	
Fully Rejected	

Version history

Version	Date	Comments
ToC	01.11.24	Draft ToC
Draft	04.12.24	Draft for review
Final	20.12.24	Final version with reviewers' comments incorporated

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Living Lab (LL) methodology in the ACCEPT project employed a user-centric co-creation approach, emphasizing iterative feedback and active end-user involvement. The framework combined top-down strategic planning with bottom-up insights from pilot site representatives, ensuring alignment between technical objectives and community needs. Despite challenges like COVID-19, the project adapted through hybrid engagement methods, maintaining continuity and inclusivity. Monthly meetings and workshops facilitated cross-collaboration, preventing siloed efforts. This deliverable summarises the key engagement activities in the LLs, their results, impact, and evaluation throughout the 48 months of the project. It also provides an updated engagement roadmap with an overview and timeline of the completed engagements.

The Capacity Building Workshops aimed to deepen understanding of energy communities and address engagement challenges such as trust deficits and resistance to change. Participants identified practical strategies, including trust-building and clear communication, to overcome these barriers. Results revealed a strong preference for social engagement strategies, which participants prioritized as key to fostering sustainable community participation.

Pilot Site Visits to pilot sites in Spain, Greece, Switzerland, and the Netherlands provided localized insights into community-specific barriers and motivations. Using the Barriers, Needs, and Opportunities (BNO) model, key findings included high societal interest in green energy, legislative hurdles, and varying levels of trust across regions. These insights informed tailored engagement strategies, enhancing participation and uptake of ACCEPT solutions.

The project created four **user personas** based on pilot site survey data: Smart Technology Persona, Financial Concerns Persona, Geopolitical Wary Persona, and Common Good Persona. These profiles reflected motivations such as cost-saving, energy independence, and environmental concerns, ensuring that engagement strategies and app features resonated with diverse user groups. Validation workshops confirmed the personas' relevance, though gender imbalance in responses highlighted the need for more inclusive data collection.

The **COM-B (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation and Behaviour) Workshops** explored barriers and drivers influencing engagement. Key barriers included lack of technical knowledge, legal constraints, and distrust in systems. Drivers included social cohesion, green consciousness, and peer influence. These findings informed actionable engagement strategies, emphasizing education, transparency, and localized approaches.

User Testing of the Citizen App (C-App) and Energy Community Platform revealed mixed results. While the app resonated with users' environmental and financial motivations, usability issues such as navigation complexity and lack of real-time data reduced satisfaction (average SUS score: 48.86). Regional disparities highlighted the need for customization, with Spanish users expressing the highest satisfaction. The Energy Community Platform scored similarly (52.78), with feedback emphasizing the need for clearer data and intuitive design.

WP3 leaders identified ten best practices of energy community creation, including understanding local contexts, conducting thorough stakeholder analyses, building trust, and tailoring communication. Flexibility was emphasized, allowing for iterative adjustments to address diverse community needs and barriers. Usability testing and inclusive approaches were critical in fostering trust and sustained engagement.

Finally, the Living Lab related KPIs are summarised and updated, highlighting the number of citizens engaged in co-creation processes and other user validation related results.

GLOSSARY

DR	Demand Response
C-APP	Citizen Application
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
WP	Work Package
SUS	System Usability Scale
COM-B	Capability Opportunity Motivation - Behaviour

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

The primary objective of Task 3.1 is to define the engagement roadmap and report on the status of the engagement activities related to the living lab (LL) process within the pilot sites. Coming to the end of the project, this final deliverable of WP3 will provide an overview of the engagement activities conducted within the lifespan of this project, and a reflection on how they shaped our continuously developing engagement approach. An update of the now complete engagement roadmap will also be provided. A final reflection on the Living Lab process will be discussed with a summary of our learnings and recommendations for future engagement efforts.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

Chapter 2 will present an update on the living lab process and provide the community engagement roadmap.

Chapter 3 will describe the completed engagements in the project (M1-48), including the engagement objective, target audience, methodology and output. The engagements will also be evaluated individually in terms of their methodology and impact on the project.

Chapter 4 will discuss the best practices on energy community creation and provide an updated list of the best practices following the activities conducted as part of WP3 in ACCEPT

Chapter 5 will evaluate the living lab process and engagements hitherto and comment on the progress towards relevant KPIs in the project

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Due to the co-creation aspect of the living lab process, there are interdependencies with most tasks and work packages within ACCEPT. Any task that requires feedback from internal or external stakeholders will be dependent on WP3. This includes activities related to the technological development of ACCEPT tools in WP5 and the pre-validation and beta testing in WP6. The LL activities in WP3 are synonymous with the pilot sites and demonstration activities performed in WP7 and are closely related to consumer validation activities reported in D7.2 and D7.3. The impact assessment and preliminary business model analysis in WP8 will also require input from the framework defined within this task, and the two work packages have closely collaborated on certain activities that will be described in more detail in deliverable 8.5. WP9 activities is also linked with this task as communication is an important intertwined element of the engagement process. The previous versions of this deliverable (D3.2, D3.3) produced detailed reports on the activities summarized here. Deliverable D3.8 describes in detail the work and analysis performed as part of the pilot site visits also summarised in this deliverable.

2. Living Lab process and the Engagement Roadmap

2.1. Introduction to Living Labs

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) defines Living Labs as user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings (Enoll.org, n.d). Westerlund et al. (2018) highlight the involvement of various stakeholders, such as researchers, citizens, companies, and local governments in these collaborative ecosystems that are Living Labs (LL).

These labs are characterized by their network structure, involving multiple actors in innovation and development activities (Hossain et al., 2019). To specify, these activities include testing, validation, development and co-creation activities in real-life settings and all stages of a design and commercialization process (Fotis et al., 2023). Additionally, they provide a space for co-generating, co-designing, and co-learning to develop tailored solutions in cooperation with stakeholders (Tukiainen et al., 2015). Living Labs can be utilized in diverse sectors including smart cities, healthcare, sustainable development, and digital technologies, among others. Living Labs commonly involve real-life testing environments and active user involvement in the innovation process, aiming to develop solutions that are both practical and impactful.

The underlying factor of why Living labs are beneficial and relevant for research and professional work related to engagement lies in their unique collaborative environment. Various stakeholders including users, researchers, companies, and local governments come together for all stages of an innovation process in real-life settings and exchange knowledge (Archibald et al., 2021). Consequently, Living Labs can be regarded as open innovation ecosystems that integrate research processes within real-world communities and practical contexts. Compagnucci et al. (2020) identify various benefits, including good practices, knowledge production and transfer, local development, trans disciplinaryity, user engagement, and creativity.

Adopting a LL approach within EU projects synergises with the European Union's focus on contributing to and promoting sustainable development where collaboration, innovation, and the potential to stimulate continuous economic growth. In recent years, the European Union has shown considerable attention and support towards Living labs, with various projects utilizing them to tackle societal challenges through collaboration, real-life experimentation, and co-creation (Lupp et al., 2020). In addition, these labs provide structure for public and private collaboration to develop new services, business ideas, and technologies, aligning with the EU's emphasis on public-private-people partnerships for innovation (Potters et al., 2022).

2.2. Accept Living Lab process

The Living Labs methodology served as a comprehensive and dynamic framework for implementing the co-creation approach central to the ACCEPT project. This methodology aimed to embed end-user needs into the core elements of a research and development initiative, such as concept testing, use case selection, business model design, and requirement definition. However, the approach goes beyond merely conceptualizing these needs. A defining characteristic of the LL methodology is its emphasis on actively involving end users throughout the design and development process via iterative feedback loops. These loops ensure that the perspectives of end users and citizens are continuously integrated at all stages of solution and business model development. This stands in contrast to traditional approaches that often consider such perspectives only at the final stages of a project (Ballon et al., 2005). By engaging stakeholders early and often, the LL methodology aligns the design channels of an innovation project with the actual needs of the end user and the market, ultimately enhancing the project's potential for successful market adoption.

To operationalize this methodology within the ACCEPT project, a hybrid collaboration approach has been employed. This approach is not only structured but also highly adaptive, providing a roadmap for engagement activities taking place throughout the project's duration. It comprises two major components that work in tandem: (1) a top-down perspective informed by input from project and technical coordinators, and (2) a bottom-up perspective focusing

on the contributions of work package (WP), task, and pilot site leaders. This dual perspective is critical for ensuring that the project's high-level objectives are closely aligned with ground-level needs and realities. Such alignment is essential for planning stakeholder engagement activities in a manner that is both effective and inclusive. Moreover, this hybrid approach played a crucial role in fostering collaboration between work packages, mitigating the risk of project partners working in silos, and ensuring the smooth integration of diverse efforts within the broader framework of the project.

The implementation of this hybrid collaboration approach is anchored in the monthly Living Lab meetings, which are convened by the leaders of WP3. These meetings were attended by representatives from each pilot site, the project management team, technical solution developers, and the communications team. They served as a central forum for discussing plans, challenges, and outcomes related to engagement activities, including pilot site visits and user testing sessions. This collaborative platform ensured that all consortium partners involved in planning and executing engagement activities are informed, aligned, and able to contribute effectively to the project's goals. In addition to these regular meetings, supplementary meetings, email exchanges, and workshops are organized as needed to address specific engagement-related requirements or challenges.

The top-down component of the hybrid approach focused on identifying the key stages in the project where stakeholder feedback is critical. To this end, project and technical coordinators provided a high-level timeline that outlined the timing, purpose, and scope of the required feedback, identified the work packages (WPs) involved, and specified whether the engagement activity would target internal or external stakeholders. Project coordinators, who have a comprehensive overview of the project's broader objectives, and technical coordinators, responsible for overseeing the development of the core technologies underpinning the ACCEPT solution, are uniquely positioned to map out the engagement activities essential to the project's success. By leveraging their insights, the top-down component ensured that engagement activities were strategically timed and aligned with the project's overarching goals.

On the other hand, the bottom-up component ensured that the perspectives, needs, and insights of task leaders, work package leaders, and pilot site representatives were adequately considered. Through questionnaires, interviews and workshops throughout the project, we gathered critical details, including the responsible partner, the timing and purpose of the engagement, the target stakeholder categories, and the methodologies to be employed. This continuous feedback loop also encouraged work package and task leaders to actively reflect on the engagement needs associated with their tasks and provided a platform for them to contribute their perspectives on the types of engagements that are necessary or anticipated, thereby fostering a sense of ownership and collaboration.

To execute these engagements effectively, a wide variety of tools and methodologies were utilised, including remote collaboration tools in response to COVID-19-related travel and social distancing restrictions. Although not exhaustive, the updated and complete Engagement roadmap outlined in Table 1 reflects the consortium's commitment to flexibility and adaptability, ensuring that engagements could proceed even under challenging circumstances. As pandemic-related restrictions eased, the ACCEPT consortium transitioned back to in-person engagements wherever possible, recognizing the value of face-to-face interactions in fostering deeper connections and more meaningful collaborations.

The selection of engagement methods was tailored to the specific objectives and scope of each activity, emphasizing a customized rather than a standardized approach. For instance, instead of mandating a fixed number of events (e.g., three workshops per pilot site), the LL framework adopts a dynamic and responsive strategy that employs a combination of engagement methodologies and tools suited to the unique needs of each pilot community. Examples of these methodologies include LL committee participation, stakeholder interviews, usability focus groups, and end-user workshops. This flexible approach ensured that engagement activities were not only aligned with the specific goals of each pilot site but also responsive to the preferences of both task leaders and the stakeholders being engaged.

This comprehensive and context-sensitive approach ensured that the Living Labs methodology is not just a tool for achieving the project's immediate objectives but also a mechanism for fostering long-term collaboration, innovation, and impact. By prioritizing flexibility, inclusivity, continuous feedback, and trust among consortium members and

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end-users the ACCEPT project leveraged the Living Labs framework to create solutions that are not only technically robust but also socially and commercially viable.

Date	Engagement activity	Description	WP(s) involved
M6	Concept test survey	Collection of market actor and prosumer feedback on ACCEPT solutions to be developed	WP2
M6	Interviews: Swiss pilot	Presenting details and recruiting key stakeholders within the community required for the ACCEPT project	WP3
M6	Workshop: Swiss pilot	Q&A session hosted by pilot partners to answer community questions about the project	WP3
M6	Interviews: Dutch pilot	Informing and recruiting end users for the ACCEPT project	WP3
M6	Interviews: Spanish pilot	Presenting details of ACCEPT and recruiting users within the community to gather feedback	WP3
M6	Workshop: Spanish pilot	Q&A session hosted by pilot partners to answer community questions about the project	WP3
M7	Workshop: Greek pilot site	Presentation and workshop event hosted in the pilot region to raise awareness and inform the community of the ACCEPT project	WP3
M10	Survey	Feedback from the pilot site representatives on business cases, use cases, system architecture and measurement & verification methodology	WP2
M10-13	Survey	Ex-ante pilot surveys to assess suitability for technical installation	WP6
M12	Survey	Feedback on service level agreements and contract terms of the business models and ACCEPT services	WP2
M16	Workshop	Capacity building workshop with consortium members to share experiences & discuss strategies regarding community engagement	WP3
M21	Pilot site visit	Spanish pilot site visit	WP3 & WP7
M22	Pilot site visit	Dutch pilot site visit	WP3 & WP7

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M22	Pilot site visit	Swiss pilot site visit	WP3 & WP7
M21-M22	Survey	Persona development questionnaire design and distribution	WP7
M23	Pilot site visit	Greek pilot site visit	WP3 & WP7
M23-24	User testing	Interviews and workshops with citizens to gather feedback on UX and UI on the citizen ACCEPT citizen APP	WP5 & WP7
M24	Communication	Project Newsletter to share results and highlights from ACCEPT with all pilot communities	WP9
M25	Workshop	Validation of the personas developed in ACCEPT with pilot leaders	WP7 & WP3
M28	Video	Creation of a project video explaining ACCEPT to be disseminated through various channels	WP9
M26	Workshop	Checkpoint meeting with WP3 leaders and each pilot partner determined pilot-specific engagement roadmaps	WP3 & WP7
M26	Communication	Sharing of results from citizen APP user testing with pilot sites	WP7
M30	Communication	Project Newsletter to share key results and developments from ACCEPT with all pilot communities	WP9
M36	Communication	Project Newsletter to share key results and developments from ACCEPT with all pilot communities	WP9
M38	Communication	Informative engagement videos about ACCEPT related terminology	WP3 & WP9
M37	Workshop	Workshop with consortium members from all pilot sites to evaluate the community engagement activities	WP8 & WP3
M40	Community engagement	COM-B workshops to evaluate engagement drivers and barriers at the Spanish pilot site	WP8 & WP3
M40	Workshop	A workshop with citizens and stakeholders external to the project to evaluate the ACCEPT approach of engagement	WP8 & WP3

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M40	Interviews	Gathering of feedback on preliminary business models from expert market actors	WP8 & WP3
M41	Communication	Informative engagement videos about ACCEPT related terminology	WP3 & WP9
M42	Community engagement	COM-B workshops to evaluate engagement drivers and barriers at the Swiss pilot site	WP8 & WP3
M43-45	User testing	Second round of user testing of Citizen App	WP7 & WP3
M45	User testing	User testing focus groups of the Energy Community Platform	WP7 & WP3
M46	Communication	Validation of the user testing results with ACCEPT consortium through LL meetings	WP7 & WP3

Table 1: Completed engagement roadmap

3. Overview of engagement activities

This chapter will provide an overview and summary of the most important engagement activities in the LL process from the beginning of the project to the end. The previous versions of this deliverable (D3.1, D3.2), elaborate on these activities in detail, in addition to WP7 and WP8 deliverables (D7.2, D7.3, D8.5). The purpose of this chapter is to summarize the aims, methods, results and impacts of these activities that were designed through the Living Lab approach over the course of 48 months, to draw a comprehensive picture of engagement efforts in the project that will guide our conclusions, lessons learnt and recommendations.

3.1. Capacity building workshop

3.1.1. Aim

The capacity-building workshop was conducted remotely during the M16 of the project by WP3 leaders. It aimed to enhance consortium partners' understanding of energy communities and their challenges. The workshop targeted 25 participants, including members from technical work packages (WP4 & WP5), pilot site representatives, and the communication team (WP9). The primary objectives were to deepen knowledge about defining energy communities, address challenges and barriers in engaging with these communities, and identify solutions for mitigating disengagement. These objectives were explored through three tasks: defining "community," identifying challenges and mitigation strategies, and prioritizing solutions to address disengagement.

3.1.2. Methodology and Results

1. Defining "Community"

This task began with a keyword exercise where participants shared their perceptions of "community" using the online tool Mentimeter. Their responses formed a word cloud, which served as the basis for a group discussion. These discussions revealed the fluid and multifaceted nature of "community," emphasizing that community formation—whether online or offline—follows predictable life cycles, including formation, consolidation, and conflict. The exercise highlighted diverse perspectives on what constitutes a community and set the stage for a shared understanding crucial for building energy communities.

2. Challenges and Mitigation Strategies in Building Energy Communities

Participants tackled two real-world scenarios representing different stages of energy projects:

- **Scenario 1:** Early-stage engagement to create local interest and recruit members for a solar cooperative.
- **Scenario 2:** Mid-project conflict over diversifying the cooperative's operations amidst members' resistance.

In smaller groups, participants used an online Miro board to brainstorm challenges and strategies for each scenario. This activity fostered knowledge-sharing, as groups presented their findings and received feedback during a plenary discussion. Key outcomes included strategies for building trust, fostering inclusivity, and clearly communicating the benefits of energy projects. These insights were critical for enhancing the consortium's collective capacity to address complex challenges in energy community creation and management.

3. Solution Prioritization for Addressing Disengagement

The final task addressed community disengagement from an energy monitoring application. Participants evaluated nine predefined solutions across three domains: social engagement, technology, and business modelling. Using Miro's voting and note-taking features, they prioritized three solutions and justified their top choice. Quantitative analysis showed a strong preference for social engagement strategies, which garnered 50% to 57% of votes, followed by technology (24% to 28%) and business modelling (19% to 22%). The most favoured solution was "Increased community engagement," followed by analysing similar technologies and researching long-term commitment strategies. These results highlighted the importance of fostering active participation and learning from previous initiatives to sustain engagement in energy projects.

3.1.3. Impact

The workshop had a significant impact on the ACCEPT consortium by fostering a deeper understanding of energy communities and providing practical strategies for engagement. It enabled participants to explore foundational concepts, such as community definitions, while addressing tangible challenges in energy project implementation. The inclusion of diverse perspectives enriched the discussion, offering a broad array of mitigation strategies that were shared and refined collaboratively.

The workshop's timing in M16 was strategic, as it allowed the consortium to integrate its findings into upcoming engagement activities. It also laid the groundwork for continued dialogue, with results presented during the M17 Living Lab (LL) monthly meeting. This sustained focus encouraged consortium partners to apply the workshop insights to real-world pilot site challenges, enhancing the overall effectiveness of community engagement efforts. While the workshop successfully built capacity at the consortium level, individual experiences varied due to differing levels of prior knowledge. For some participants, the workshop served as a learning experience, while for others, it acted more as a knowledge-sharing platform. Despite this, the collective benefit to the consortium was substantial, as it harnessed diverse expertise to strengthen the overall approach to community engagement.

3.1.4. Evaluation

The workshop proved valuable in identifying key challenges, strategies, and solutions for engaging energy communities. It improved the consortium's understanding of community dynamics and emphasized the importance of tailoring engagement approaches to specific contexts. The interactive and collaborative methodology fostered knowledge-sharing and capacity building, equipping partners to address engagement challenges more effectively. However, limitations were noted. Some participants may have felt the workshop content was too basic, given their advanced experience, while others found it highly beneficial. Additionally, the quantitative analysis of solution prioritization revealed potential bias, as participants may have selected socially-focused solutions due to the workshop's emphasis on community engagement. Future iterations of similar workshops could address these issues by customizing content to participants' expertise levels and exploring solutions in a neutral context.

3.1.5. Conclusion

The capacity-building workshop succeeded in achieving its aims of enhancing consortium members' understanding of energy communities and equipping them with strategies to address engagement challenges. Through a mix of qualitative and quantitative exercises, participants gained practical insights into community dynamics, barriers to engagement, and solutions for overcoming disengagement. While some limitations were noted, the workshop's collaborative approach significantly contributed to the ACCEPT project's objectives and fostered a foundation for ongoing dialogue and innovation in energy community engagement.

3.2. Pilot site visits

3.2.1. Aim

The pilot site visits were conducted by WP3 leaders with the goal of gathering information and insights into the specific contexts, cultures, and stakeholders of the ACCEPT pilot communities. Understanding these factors is critical for planning engagement activities tailored to local needs and barriers. These targeted activities are designed to encourage participation from citizens and stakeholders within energy communities and to promote the adoption of ACCEPT solutions and services.

3.2.2. Methodology

The methodology for the pilot site visits consisted of two main components:

1. **Tours of Pilot Regions:** Local pilot partners guided WP3 leaders through the pilot areas, providing firsthand opportunities to observe the community context, assets, and environmental factors.

2. **Stakeholder Interactions:** Meetings, interviews, focus groups, and workshops were conducted with local stakeholders and citizens to gain insights into community motivations, barriers, and perspectives on green energy.

The collected data were analysed using the Barriers, Needs, and Opportunities (BNO) model. This framework assesses the macro and micro elements of energy communities to identify behavioural change triggers, which are then used to shape the engagement roadmap. The methodology was consistent across all pilot sites, but specific activities and results varied based on local contexts.

3.2.3. Results

1. SPANISH PILOT SITE VISIT

Conducted over two days in M21, this visit included a tour of the Santomera and Murcia regions. Activities included interviews with an energy expert and two focus groups with local citizens (prosumers and end users). The BNO analysis identified several key change triggers:

- Strong societal appeal and interest in green energy
- Opportunities for collaboration with local experts
- Increasing interest in photovoltaic (PV) panels
- Need for clarity on ACCEPT's benefits (short- and long-term)
- Legislative and bureaucratic challenges
- Climate change as a primary motivator; monetary benefits as secondary
- Importance of clear and consistent information flow
- Varied opinions on demand response (control vs. automation)
- Rising energy costs as a catalyst for change

2. DUTCH PILOT SITE VISIT

Held over two days in M22, the visit included a tour of the Lanxmeer community and a project kick-off meeting with 20 participants. The meeting featured a presentation on the ACCEPT project and a workshop on energy use motivations. The BNO analysis highlighted the following change triggers:

- Validation of persona profiles
- Integration with existing community-led projects (e.g., Thermo Bello)
- Enhanced collaboration between ACCEPT and the community
- Climate change as a priority in decision-making
- Collective participation in innovation
- Enjoyment as a factor in services and research
- Privacy considerations

3. SWISS PILOT SITE VISIT

Completed over two days in M22, the visit included a tour of the Massagno community and five interviews with local stakeholders, including a chief financial officer and community prosumers. The BNO analysis revealed these key triggers:

- Community interest in climate-focused innovation
- Need for forums to foster discussion and awareness
- Clarity on demand response (control and implications)
- Importance of trust-building
- Incorporation of existing business operations into ACCEPT for long-term impact
- Regular information flow and knowledge-sharing
- Opportunities for education and awareness through communal spaces

4. GREEK PILOT SITE VISIT

Conducted over two days in M23, this visit included a tour of the Protergia office in Athens and the Aspra Spitia region. Activities included a focus group with energy experts and interviews with citizens who also worked at a local factory. Key change triggers identified through the BNO analysis included:

- Regular and engaging participation to sustain interest
- Emphasis on safety aspects
- Interconnection between community, industry, and lifestyle
- Interest in broader EU innovation projects

3.2.4. Impact

The pilot site visits provided invaluable insights into the unique contexts of each community, enabling the development of a localized and effective engagement roadmap. By combining consistent methodologies with site-specific flexibility, the visits ensured that engagement strategies aligned with the cultural, environmental, and motivational dynamics of each region.

The BNO model played a critical role in identifying behavioural change triggers and focus areas for engagement. These findings ensure that future activities connect with the specific needs and contexts of each community, fostering stronger relationships between citizens and the ACCEPT project.

Additionally, the knowledge gained from the site visits informed the checkpoint meetings in M26, facilitating tailored engagements that maximize community participation and uptake of ACCEPT solutions. The visits also demonstrated the importance of balancing standardized processes with adaptability to local conditions, reinforcing the ACCEPT project's commitment to community-centred innovation.

Despite the consistent methodology, variations in site conditions highlighted the importance of leveraging local strengths. For instance, the Dutch site benefited from a pre-existing culture of green energy, enabling large-scale community workshops, while other sites focused on smaller, more targeted interactions.

3.2.5. Evaluation

The pilot site visits were a cornerstone for planning effective, community-specific engagement activities. They significantly contributed to building trust with the communities, bring the project closer to them and made them feel valued and heard. By addressing local barriers and leveraging unique opportunities, these visits significantly contributed to ACCEPT's engagement efforts.

3.2.6. Conclusion

The pilot site visits were instrumental in laying the groundwork for community-centred engagement within the ACCEPT project. By combining a structured methodology with site-specific adaptability, the visits allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the diverse contexts, cultures, and challenges present in each pilot region. The insights gained through tours, stakeholder interactions, and the application of the BNO model provided a robust foundation for tailoring engagement strategies to local needs and priorities.

The findings highlighted the importance of addressing unique barriers, leveraging existing community strengths, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Common themes, such as the need for clear communication, trust-building, and aligning with local motivations like climate change and cost-saving, emerged as critical factors in shaping effective strategies. Furthermore, the differences across pilot sites underscored the value of balancing standardized approaches with flexibility to accommodate local dynamics.

Overall, the pilot site visits marked a pivotal step in ensuring that ACCEPT's solutions are not only technically robust but also socially and culturally aligned. These efforts enhanced the project's ability to foster meaningful participation and drive the adoption of sustainable energy practices across diverse communities.

3.3. Persona Development

3.3.1. Aim

The persona development initiative in the ACCEPT project aimed to provide a deeper understanding of the communities involved by creating user personas rooted in real-life data. Inspired by Cooper's (1999) introduction of personas to address user-centric software design, this approach was adapted to represent the diverse needs, motivations, and challenges of the pilot communities. Personas were developed to bridge cultural and contextual differences and avoid the pitfalls of one-size-fits-all strategies often seen in environmental communication.

These personas not only guided engagement planning but also informed the design of the Citizen App (C-App), ensuring it resonated with end users. By basing personas on survey data from pilot communities, the ACCEPT project ensured that its engagement strategies and app features were customized to reflect the realities of its users.

3.3.2. Methodology

PERSONA DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

The development process involved four main stages:

1. **Survey Design:** A tailored questionnaire was created using insights from pilot site visits and literature.
2. **Survey Distribution:** The survey was distributed to participants in the pilot communities.
3. **Data Analysis:** Responses were analysed using both qualitative and quantitative methods.
4. **Persona Creation:** The findings were synthesized into detailed persona profiles.

By M26, the personas were validated through checkpoint meetings with pilot leaders to ensure their relevance and accuracy.

SURVEY DESIGN AND EXECUTION

The survey design combined qualitative and quantitative approaches. Open-ended questions explored motivations for energy behaviour and flexibility in daily comfort concerning smart home automation. Quantitative questions focused on six key motivational areas: environmental interest, knowledge-seeking, technological interest, political alignment, social drivers, and financial concerns.

The survey was distributed across four pilot sites in Greece, Spain, the Netherlands, and Switzerland, receiving 110 responses. The questionnaire was translated into local languages, and the responses were analysed using thematic analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). PCA revealed motivational components that grouped user preferences, forming the foundation for persona creation.

3.3.3. Results

PERSONA PROFILES

Four personas were developed, each representing key motivational drivers and barriers:

1. **Smart Technology Persona:**
 - Motivated by knowledge, smart home technologies, and new gadgets.
 - Prefers data-driven insights and interactive learning features.
 - Predominantly present in Greece and the Netherlands, with some presence in Switzerland.
2. **Financial Concerns Persona:**
 - Driven by cost-saving opportunities and rising energy prices.
 - Focused on monetary benefits and clear financial data.
 - Dominantly Greek with minor Swiss representation.
3. **Geopolitical Wary Persona:**
 - Concerned with energy independence and security.
 - Seeks autonomy from geopolitical influences and large energy providers.
 - Predominantly Spanish, with strong Dutch representation.

4. Common Good Persona:

- Motivated by environmental conservation and community involvement.
- Prioritizes collective action and social recognition.
- Most common in Dutch communities, with representation in Greece and Spain.

3.3.4. Validation Workshops

GENERAL ASSEMBLY WORKSHOP

During the 4th General Assembly in Cartagena (M25), a workshop titled "Community Engagement, Policy, and Socio-Economic Concerns" validated the personas and further refined engagement plans. Participants created hypothetical personas for each pilot site, integrating socio-economic factors and discussing key motivations and barriers.

Activities included:

- Rating motivational factors for each pilot site.
- Developing detailed user profiles for pilot countries.
- Presenting personas in a first-person narrative to foster collaborative insights.

The workshop emphasized the diverse drivers and barriers across pilot sites and offered new perspectives for tailoring engagement strategies.

CHECKPOINT MEETINGS

In M26, separate checkpoint meetings with pilot leaders validated the personas against firsthand community experiences. Discussions focused on:

- Unique cultural and socio-economic characteristics.
- Major barriers, including reluctance to use the C-App and limited awareness of the broader project goals.
- Co-created solutions, timelines, and success metrics using Miro boards.

Two primary barriers were identified:

1. **Reluctance to Use the C-App:** Users found the app complex and unmotivating.
2. **Lack of Awareness:** Communities needed clarity on key project goals and terminology, such as demand response and energy communities.

These insights informed practical recommendations for engagement and app improvements.

3.3.5. Impact

C-APP RECOMMENDATIONS

The persona profiles guided app feature development to align with user motivations:

- **Smart Technology Persona:** Interactive quizzes, energy-related fun facts, and gamification elements tailored to knowledge-seekers.
- **Financial Concerns Persona:** Clear cost-saving data and finance-focused features.
- **Common Good Persona:** Community competitions, social progress visualizations, and engagement metrics emphasizing environmental goals.
- **Geopolitical Wary Persona:** Features highlighting energy independence and autonomy.

Gamification ideas included customizable app elements (e.g., themes, visual progress indicators) to sustain user interest.

AWARENESS VIDEO RECOMMENDATIONS

To address limited awareness, WP3 leaders proposed animated videos featuring personas to explain complex concepts like demand response and energy communities. These videos were created by WP9 leaders and were made available in local languages to ensure accessibility.

3.3.6. Evaluation

Persona development proved to be a valuable methodology to create a common understanding among the consortium about our pilot communities and their motivations. However, they are not without limitation. Although they provide us with relatable user profiles, it is important to emphasize that not all users fit into these descriptions. Furthermore, our study had a representativity limitation, namely that all personas turned out to be male due to a gender imbalance among survey respondents. We have emphasized that this means that these personas are not representative of the entire ACCEPT community, only of the most active members. Gender-specific energy behaviours need to be acknowledged and improving gender inclusivity in future data collection efforts were emphasized when communicating the results.

3.3.7. Conclusion

The persona development process provided a nuanced understanding of the ACCEPT pilot communities, allowing tailored engagement strategies and user-centric app features. While the personas reflect broad motivational trends, individual users may embody multiple personas or fall outside these archetypes. As such, the personas serve as flexible guidelines rather than rigid categories.

The personas also fostered collaboration within the consortium by creating a shared language for discussing user motivations and challenges. This approach continues to guide engagement planning, ensuring that the ACCEPT project's solutions resonate with diverse community needs and promote meaningful participation in energy transitions.

3.4. COM-B Workshops: Drivers and Barriers of Engagement

3.4.1. Aims

The series of workshops held in Thessaloniki, Murcia, Bullas, and Lugano aimed to identify and understand the key drivers and barriers to community engagement with the ACCEPT project. Using the COM-B model of behaviour change, these workshops sought to uncover the psychological, social, and environmental factors influencing participation in energy communities and the uptake of project solutions. By engaging different stakeholders—ranging from project consortium members and end-users to non-participating citizens and industry professionals—the workshops aimed to inform tailored engagement strategies and improve project outcomes. The methodology, results, and implications of these workshops are comprehensively detailed in D8.5. Here, we provide a concise summary to complement the broader overview of engagement activities presented in this document, offering a cohesive perspective on the project's efforts throughout its duration.

3.4.2. Methods

Each workshop was designed to facilitate group discussions using the COM-B model framework (Michie et al., 2011), focusing on three components of behaviour: Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation. Participants were grouped based on their affiliations or roles (e.g., pilot leaders, citizens, industry professionals) and worked through templates to identify and prioritize drivers and barriers specific to their contexts. The outputs were synthesized to provide actionable insights for addressing engagement challenges.

1. **Consortium (January 2024):** Targeted the project consortium during 6th General Assembly in Thessaloniki, with groups from each pilot site identifying engagement barriers and drivers.

2. **Murcia End-users Workshop (April 2024):** Engaged residents of the Murcia pilot community to discuss their perspectives on energy communities.
3. **Bullas External Citizens Workshop:** Focused on non-participating citizens to understand barriers and drivers from an external perspective.
4. **Lugano Industry Stakeholders Workshop:** Brought in industry and business stakeholders to explore their experiences in engaging with citizens.

3.4.3. Results

CONSORTIUM WORKSHOP

This workshop highlighted significant **barriers** across the COM-B framework:

- **Capability:** Lack of resources, technical skills, and concerns about personal data; elderly citizens faced challenges in adapting to new technologies.
- **Opportunity:** Safety concerns, limited access to solutions, and a lack of trust and communication within communities.
- **Motivation:** Low incentives, doubts about solution efficiency, and idle project time leading to disengagement.

Drivers identified included environmental motivations, social cohesion, and the desire to participate in community-driven solutions.

MURCIA END-USERS WORKSHOP

The Murcia workshop focused on end-user perspectives, revealing the following **barriers**:

- **Capability:** Information deficits on regulations and technology, coupled with resistance to change.
- **Opportunity:** Privileged sectors hindering energy community development and unreliable sources of information.
- **Motivation:** Prioritization of energy costs over environmental concerns and lack of attention to disadvantaged groups.

Potential **drivers** discussed included:

- **Capability:** Existing knowledge about climate change as a foundation.
- **Opportunity:** Peer influence through committed neighbours, broadcast media showcasing successful energy communities, and standardized European processes.
- **Motivation:** The urgency of proper energy management and trust-building within energy communities.

BULLAS EXTERNAL CITIZENS WORKSHOP

This session captured the views of non-ACCEPT-participating citizens, with key **barriers** including:

- **Capability:** Lack of legal and bureaucratic knowledge required for forming or joining energy communities.
- **Opportunity:** Bureaucratic hurdles, lengthy decision-making processes, and legal constraints.
- **Motivation:** Limited understanding of energy-sharing mechanisms and distrust in bureaucratic and economic systems.

Drivers identified were:

- **Capability:** Availability of experts and advisors to assist participants.
- **Opportunity:** Strong leadership, examples of successful energy communities, and case studies to inspire engagement.
- **Motivation:** Green conscience and transparency in energy community processes.

LUGANO INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDERS WORKSHOP

Industry stakeholders in Lugano provided insights into **barriers** such as:

- **Capability:** Limited understanding of technical laws and reluctance among elderly citizens to engage with climate-related solutions.
- **Opportunity:** Frequent legal changes, societal uncertainty, and lack of time.
- **Motivation:** Low electricity costs and high salaries in Switzerland diminishing interest, and difficulty in explaining rules and benefits to participants.

Drivers included:

- **Capability:** Development of an end-user app and inclusion of trusted entities to improve psychological capabilities.
- **Opportunity:** Joining energy communities as a neighbourhood activity, direct contact with customers, green public perception, and new research opportunities.
- **Motivation:** Increased user education and the development of new products and services.

3.4.4. Impact

The workshops provided valuable insights into the multifaceted barriers and drivers influencing engagement with energy communities. By addressing capability gaps (e.g., lack of knowledge and technical skills), improving opportunities (e.g., trust-building and accessibility of solutions), and enhancing motivational factors (e.g., financial incentives and environmental consciousness), the ACCEPT project can design more effective engagement strategies.

Key outcomes included:

- Identifying the importance of targeted education and information dissemination to address knowledge gaps.
- Emphasizing the role of trusted leadership and peer influence in fostering community participation.
- Recognizing the need for transparency, standardized processes, and visible success stories to build trust and motivation.

3.4.5. Evaluation

The workshops were instrumental in capturing diverse perspectives from different stakeholder groups. They revealed common barriers, such as lack of knowledge, legal constraints, and insufficient motivation, alongside unique drivers like ecological consciousness and social cohesion. In addition, addressing entrenched resistance to change and adapting solutions to varying local contexts remain a challenge.

By leveraging these insights, the ACCEPT project can evaluate its engagement strategies and make recommendations for future efforts (detailed in D8.5). Most importantly emphasize the need for a holistic approach that addresses behavioural, social, and systemic factors to drive sustainable participation in energy communities.

3.4.6. Conclusion

By applying the COM-B model to diverse stakeholder groups across multiple locations, the workshops uncovered shared challenges—such as capability gaps, trust issues, and motivational barriers—while also identifying localized drivers, such as community leadership, ecological consciousness, and peer influence.

These findings underscore the importance of a tailored approach to engagement that accounts for the unique contexts and priorities of each community. Addressing barriers like knowledge deficits, bureaucratic hurdles, and resistance to change requires targeted educational efforts, transparent communication, and the development of accessible, user-friendly solutions. Simultaneously, leveraging drivers such as environmental motivations, social cohesion, and visible success stories can foster a sense of trust and shared purpose.

The workshops highlighted the need for collaboration among stakeholders, trusted leadership, and standardized processes to build momentum for sustainable energy practices. As a foundation for future engagement strategies,

these insights will enable the ACCEPT project to refine its efforts, ensuring they are inclusive, impactful, and aligned with the needs of diverse communities.

3.5. User testing

3.5.1. Aims

User testing within the ACCEPT project aimed to ensure the Citizen App (C-App) and Energy Community Platform were user-centric, functional, and met the needs of end-users and pilot leaders. The process sought to identify motivations, perceived advantages and disadvantages of the technology to foster engagement and ownership among users, and to be able to provide actionable feedback for improvement to technical partners. By involving both community members and consortium stakeholders, the testing aimed to ensure that the technologies would facilitate participation in energy communities and support energy transition initiatives effectively. The details of the first user testing sessions of the earlier version of the app are detailed in D3.3, and the final user testing report can be found in D7.3, Consumer validation report v3.

3.5.2. Methods

The user testing followed a structured roadmap that involved iterative feedback from internal and external stakeholders across multiple stages. The methodology combined qualitative and quantitative approaches, including thematic analysis, the System Usability Scale (SUS), focus groups, and interactive workshops.

1. **Internal Technical Feedback (M15):** Initial feedback from technical partners on the alpha version of the C-App focused on design and functionality.
2. **Site Visits (M21–M24):** Community workshops, interviews, and focus groups were conducted to gather user expectations and create a "wish list" for the app.
3. **Initial External User Testing (M23):** Pilot partners engaged end-users in testing sessions, collecting insights through thematic analysis and SUS scoring.
4. **Final User Testing (M43–M45):** Conducted by Hamilton Global, a professional market research firm, the final round included standardized focus groups for both the C-App and Energy Community Platform, involving end-users and pilot leaders.

3.5.3. Results

The different stages of the user testing revealed various barriers, suggestions and wishes regarding the application, alongside with its perceived advantages.

CITIZEN APP (C-APP)

1. Initial Internal Feedback

- **Barriers:** Overwhelming information, unclear demand response (DR) communication, and the need for simplified navigation.
- **Suggestions:** Gamification, better-organized dashboards, and improved business model integration.

2. Site Visit Feedback

- **User Wishlist:** A visually appealing, user-friendly app with features like energy consumption monitoring, real-time notifications, and energy education.

3. Initial External User Testing

- **Thematic Analysis Results:**
 - **Usability Challenges:** Complexity and navigation issues.
 - **Missing Features:** Requests for additional functionalities and data.
 - **Positive Aspects:** Appreciation for color-coded visual cues and DR functionality.
 - **Average SUS Score:** 56.38 (Below Average), with significant variation across pilot sites.

4. Final User Testing

- **Motivations Identified:**
 - Environmental concerns, energy cost savings, and autonomy from large corporations.
 - Social engagement and interest in innovative energy technologies.
- **Advantages:**
 - Simple interface, intuitive visual design, and basic energy monitoring capabilities.
- **Barriers:**
 - Limited connectivity of household devices.
 - Lack of real-time data and overly technical information.
 - Usability issues, including session login difficulties and unclear navigation.
- **Ideal App Features:** Simplicity, local language support, intuitive design, predictive analytics, and integration of smart devices.

SUS Score Trends: System Usability Scale was used to conduct a quantitative assessment on the usability of the application (see the scale in Appendix A). The final testing saw a decline in satisfaction (average score: 48.86), reflecting unmet expectations despite updates. Spanish users remained most satisfied, while others expressed significant dissatisfaction due to technical and usability issues. The results are likely a reflection to the fact that the C-App was not complete at the time of the testing and many participants had no chance to meaningfully engage with the App prior to the testing, due to lack of data or connectivity issues. More details can be found in D7.3.

	First testing (M23)		Second testing (M43)	
Country	Participants	Average Score	Participants	Average Score
Spain	4	86.25 ●	9	71.39 ●
Switzerland	3	37.50 ●	Didn't participate	
Netherlands	11	32.73 ●	9	35.28 ●
Greece	20	66.25 ●	4	28.75 ●
Combined average	38	56.38 ●	22	48.86 ●

Table 2: Comparison of SUS results for C-APP over time

ENERGY COMMUNITY PLATFORM

Pilot leader Focus Group Feedback:

- Appreciated its potential for fostering community engagement and providing actionable insights.
- Criticized inconsistent data and unclear concepts, particularly related to "Baseline, Actual, and Optimal" indicators.
- Suggested improvements for data reliability, user notifications, and intuitive design.

SUS Score: The platform scored an average of 52.78, indicating moderate dissatisfaction, with Dutch and Swiss users expressing lower satisfaction compared to Greek and Spanish users. Similarly to the C-App, the readiness of the application at the time of the testing was likely a contributing factor to the relatively low SUS scores.

Group	Participants	Average SUS Score
Netherlands & Switzerland	6	47.50 ●
Greece & Spain	3	63.33 ●
Combined average	9	52.78 ●

Table 3: SUS results of the Energy Community Platform

Ideal Platform Features: Pilot leaders emphasized the need for descriptive information, real-time updates, benchmarks, and actionable recommendations to support energy optimization and community engagement.

3.5.4. Impact

The user testing provided critical insights into both applications, highlighting strengths, weaknesses, and user expectations. Key outcomes include:

1. **Alignment with User Motivations:** The C-App's environmental, economic, and social features resonate with the project's goals and the personas developed earlier in the project.
2. **Enhanced Community Engagement:** Feedback emphasized the importance of fostering a sense of belonging and ownership within energy communities.
3. **Guidance for Refinement:** The insights shaped actionable recommendations, such as simplifying interfaces, improving data accuracy, and introducing gamification.

3.5.5. Evaluation

The testing process revealed significant gaps in usability and functionality:

1. **C-App Challenges:**
 - Complexity and technical barriers limited user engagement.
 - Disconnection between user expectations and delivered features, particularly in real-time data and predictive analytics.
 - Regional disparities in satisfaction highlighted the need for tailored approaches.
2. **Energy Community Platform Issues:**
 - Data inconsistencies and unclear indicators undermined trust.
 - Pilot leaders called for improved user guidance and benchmarks.

Despite these challenges, the feedback reinforced the relevance of the project's goals and provided a roadmap for future improvements. Users valued the initiative's environmental focus and recognized its potential to empower communities.

3.5.6. Conclusion

The user testing validated the core motivations behind the ACCEPT project but underscored the need for further development to meet user expectations. The C-App and Energy Community Platform hold promise for advancing energy communities, but their success depends on addressing identified barriers, improving usability, and aligning features with user needs.

Key takeaways for future iterations include:

- Simplifying technical interfaces and providing clearer, localized instructions.
- Enhancing device connectivity and real-time data functionality.
- Incorporating user feedback into design updates and fostering transparency.

While current satisfaction levels highlight areas for improvement, the testing process provided invaluable insights for creating user-centric, impactful solutions that drive participation in energy communities and support the energy transition.

4. Best practices for community creation

This section presents a comprehensive set of recommendations derived from the living lab activities conducted as part of the ACCEPT H2020 project. Drawing from both practitioner insights and the existing literature, it outlines best practice guidelines for community engagement in demand response initiatives. These recommendations reflect the project's iterative and co-creative ethos, incorporating lessons learned from both research and direct user interactions.

In this final report, the suite of best practices has been finalized, integrating practitioner-based insights with the literature-based recommendations previously established. These practical guidelines were refined through continuous assessment and real-world application during the project, demonstrating the need for flexibility and adaptability in such dynamic research environments. The iterative evaluation of methodologies and practices has

been integral to the development process, ensuring that they remain responsive and effective in meeting project goals.

Table 4 summarizes the best practices identified for demand response projects. These recommendations represent the culmination of the ACCEPT project's findings, integrating empirical practitioner insights with robust evidence from the literature to offer a well-rounded and actionable framework for community engagement in energy initiatives.

Best practices for energy community creation	
1. Understanding the community and stakeholders	Following the work conducted in the first year of the project, it is clear that there is a necessity for implementing a LL process that allows for clear assessment and subsequent planning of engagements that will be key to creating an energy community in relation to renewable energy innovations and projects. When introducing new technologies or initiatives, it is essential to understand the local context in terms of its community objectives and the perspective of the stakeholders. The practical evidence that demonstrates the need for understanding the community and its stakeholders is reflected in the hybrid approach and site visits conducted as part of the LL process in ACCEPT.
2. Identify (genuine) stakeholders	Not all stakeholders experience the degree of impact or possess the same level of capacity to influence the process. Therefore, a rigorous stakeholder analysis must be undertaken to establish which stakeholders are willing to share the risks involved with community engagement (Watson, 2008). These risks do not necessarily just involve financial risk but can include those relating to establishing relationships, building credibility <i>etc.</i> Stakeholders can be public institutions/services, business interests, and private citizens.
3. Establish who is an ally in the engagement process	Deepening alliances is an important factor in establishing viable community energy projects (Watson, 2008). Knowing who has a genuine interest in the successful implementation of the project is as important as identifying who might be against its success. In addition, not alienating community members that are neutral or have no specific goal for or against the project is important.
4. Establish trust	Trust (and the lack thereof) is an often-neglected aspect of community engagement, especially on the part of project leads. This is surprising given the significant impact on relationships from the very start. As Lennon <i>et al.</i> (2021) point out, a "lack of trust in local authorities and energy developers has led to difficulties in leveraging partnerships, which are often critical for accessing funding and knowledge sharing". Therefore, it is important to understand the level of trust that exists between communities and stakeholders and plan engagement activities accordingly.
5. Build capacity	A key aspect of any participative engagement process is the need to build the capacity of those communities being engaged with (King and Cruickshank 2012). The contingencies arising from the changing power dynamics between the community and say project leads often see 'power' staying with the project leads and communities left without any meaningful say in the process. Building the capacity of participants within the community to cope with the many demands associated with contributing to an energy project is essential if communities are to have any real influence or impact in the process.
6. Communication and Education	One of our main learnings from the checkpoint meetings, user testing focus groups and COM-B workshops was that a major barrier in engaging with energy communities was the lack of understanding, may that be of overarching terminologies such as Energy Community and Demand response, or specific panels and their functions in the C-App. Clear non-technical

	explanations of complex concepts need to be provided, plus it is essential to localize content to the native language and cultural context of the community, ensuring accessibility and comprehension.
7. Addressing Barriers	While many aspects of the project need to be planned well in advance, we have learned that flexibility is the greatest asset in our approach. Identifying psychological, technical, and logistical barriers through early and iterative feedback from stakeholders is key to being able to provide resources, such as training on digital tools and assistance with bureaucratic or legal requirements, to overcome barriers.
8. Usability of Digital Tools	In order to avoid frustration with the technology in the community, design apps and platforms that need to be intuitive, visually appealing, and aligned with user needs. Based on our user testing results, we need to focus on simplicity and ease of navigation, with clear pathways for accessing key functionalities. It was key in the Living Lab approach to test digital tools iteratively with diverse user groups so our recommendation can be based on the wishes of real users, who thus feel empowered and heard in the design process.
9. Measure motivations, promote impact	Forcing solutions on the community that do not align with their intrinsic motivations and norms would be incredibly challenging and counterproductive. During the project, we assessed motivations for energy community formation and found that social and environmental factors are just as important for most as monetary gains. To foster active community participation, the best path is to first assess the existing norms, attitudes and motivations, so the most attractive impact of the project can be promoted to users later on, for example emphasizing the collective impact of energy communities, fostering a sense of belonging and shared purpose.
10. Foster inclusivity	It is also essential to promote inclusivity with regard to the new technologies and their purpose. The consideration of the gender dimension is especially important in energy projects because it has been shown that men and women have different needs and preferences when it comes to different energy related decisions, e.g., temperature in the building, automation of home energy devices, amount of detail to be provided on energy consumption of the household, etc. (Tuladhar, 2020). Our site visits also revealed that different genders expressed opposing wishes regarding the automation of smart devices, even within the same household. Age is another important factor that we need to be mindful of when promoting new technology and exploring motivations, as elderly citizens might have very different preferences and understanding than the younger generations. Projects need to be careful not to forget that for successful energy community formation, all members of the community need to be considered, not just the most active ones.

Table 4: Best practices of energy community creation

5. Evaluation & conclusions

5.1. KPIs

In addition to the general evaluation of the LL activities above, the assessment of the KPIs associated with the LL process is complete.

As part of the iterative engagement process, the methodology for KPI calculations must be periodically updated to ensure accuracy and relevance. The first KPI, "Number of stakeholders participating in the co-creation process"

LIVING LAB ACTIVITIES PLAN AND EVALUATION REPORT

(target: 1,000), encompasses all stakeholders who have contributed to the project, either through active participation or feedback sessions. This KPI was calculated from the initial phases of the engagement strategy. The second KPI, "Citizens actively engaged in validation activities" (target: over 770), focuses on participation in validation activities, which are an integral component of the co-creation process. Since these activities are inherently connected and form a sequential process under the co-creation umbrella, rather than operating as separate entities, this KPI was not calculated from the very beginning of the project, when there was no service to validate yet. Consequently, the final figure achieved for the second KPI (868) is included within the total achieved under the first KPI (1221), reflecting the progressive nature of stakeholder engagement and validation efforts.

The number of citizens involved in validation activities involve participants who contributed to the persona creation and user testing sessions, community meetings, trainings, feedback sessions. The number of stakeholders participating in the co-creation process involves all stakeholders participating in the validation activities, plus stakeholders participating in workshops, focus groups and feedback sessions in the initial phases of the project. For the best practices for energy community creation, 5 more practices have been added since the last version of the deliverable, bringing the total number to 10 out of the 10 required. These practices (detailed in section 4 of this deliverable) were based on our experiences and lessons learned during the project and our engagements with the citizens of these communities.

The Net Promoter Score (NPS) is reported as a score rather than a percentage. According to Bain & Company's guidelines (Reichheld, Darnell & Burns, 2021), calculating NPS involves a simple approach: it is determined by subtracting the percentage of customers categorized as "Detractors" from the percentage categorized as "Promoters," based on their responses to a single question about their likelihood to recommend a solution to others. This scoring system ranges from -100 (if all respondents are Detractors) to +100 (if all are Promoters) (Adams et al., 2022). Scores are classified as follows: 0-19 is considered good, 20-49 is favourable, 50-79 is excellent, and 80+ is world-class. Initially, the ACCEPT Grant Agreement set the target at 75%, but this was later adjusted to 50-79 to align with the excellent range. With an achieved score of 34, our NPS falls within the favourable range. The KPIs related to net promoter score (NPS), citizen satisfaction with the ACCEPT solution and conscious acceptance of the ACCEPT solution are detailed and interpreted in D7.3 and reported here as well in table 5.

KPI	Target	Description	M12 status	M24 status	M47 status
Stakeholders participating in the co-creation process	1000	<i>Stakeholders who contributed feedback affecting the development of the solutions and services of ACCEPT</i>	353	682	1221
Citizens actively engaged in validation activities	>770	<i>Participants directly involved in ACCEPT</i>	-	329	868
Net Promoter Score (NPS) among pilot participants	50-79	<i>Score calculated for citizens' indicated willingness to recommend the ACCEPT solution to others</i>	-	-	34
Citizen satisfaction from ACCEPT solution	>75%	<i>This percentage shows how satisfied the citizens are with the project</i>	-	-	72%
Conscious acceptance of Smart Home control automation	>90%	<i>This percentage shows how the citizens willingly accept the Smart Home control automatization</i>	-	-	78%
10 best practices for energy community creation	10	<i>Validated during the ACCEPT citizen engagement activities.</i>	1	5	10

Table 5: Living Lab-related KPIs

The KPI for "Citizen time spent on the ACCEPT app" presented certain challenges in its calculation. The original definition of this KPI requires the measurement of daily time spent on the app, with a target of 10 minutes per day. However, this target was established under the assumption of a fully operational app being used daily by community members.

At this stage of the application's development, daily usage within the ACCEPT communities has not yet been achieved, which diminishes the significance of calculating this KPI as originally defined.

Instead, we focused on the period during which the app was actively tested, as this timeframe required intentional engagement from users. Using Google Analytics, we calculated alternative KPIs for the period from the 1st to the 31st of July including:

- Number of active users
- Number of sessions
- Average time per session
- Average engagement time per active user

As shown in Table 6, during this testing phase, users were not required to engage with the app daily. Instead, the average usage frequency was **1-2 times per week**, with an average session duration of **3.5 minutes**.

KPI	M43-45
Number of active users	70
Number of sessions	329
Average time per session	3m 48s
Average engagement time per active user	17m 52s

Table 6: User activity in the C-App in July 2024

5.2. General Conclusions

The ACCEPT project's use of the Living Lab (LL) approach and its extensive engagement roadmap provide a valuable case study of how co-creation methodologies can enhance community participation, promote energy transitions, and ensure user-centred design. As the final stage of this initiative, it is critical to evaluate the successes and challenges of the LL methodology while extracting lessons that can inform future projects.

The Living Lab approach demonstrated significant potential as a framework for fostering innovation and collaboration within real-world settings. Its emphasis on iterative feedback and stakeholder involvement ensured that solutions were not only technically sound but also resonated with the communities they aimed to serve. The dual perspective of top-down strategic planning combined with bottom-up contextual understanding was particularly effective in aligning project objectives with the lived realities of pilot communities. This hybrid approach mitigated the risk of siloed efforts and allowed for the incorporation of diverse perspectives, fostering a sense of ownership and inclusivity among stakeholders.

One of the major strengths of the LL methodology was its adaptability. The ability to tailor engagement strategies to the unique socio-cultural and economic contexts of each pilot site proved invaluable. For example, site visits highlighted the varying levels of trust, motivations, and barriers present across communities in Spain, Switzerland, Greece, and the Netherlands. The flexibility of the methodology allowed these insights to be directly integrated into the engagement roadmap, ensuring that each site received the support it needed. This adaptability extended to the tools and methods used; during the COVID-19 pandemic, remote collaboration tools were leveraged effectively to maintain momentum despite restrictions.

However, the LL approach was not without its challenges. One significant limitation was the uneven capacity and willingness of stakeholders to engage. While some communities demonstrated high levels of interest and participation, others were hindered by technical barriers, or scepticism about the benefits of the project. These disparities highlighted the need for more robust capacity-building measures at the outset to ensure all stakeholders are equipped to engage meaningfully. Additionally, the reliance on iterative feedback loops, while valuable, sometimes led to delays in decision-making, as diverse inputs needed to be reconciled.

Another lesson from the ACCEPT project was the importance of communication and education in overcoming barriers to engagement. Many community members struggled to understand complex concepts such as "demand response" or the benefits of energy communities. This lack of understanding often translated into resistance to participating in pilot activities or adopting new technologies. The project's localized, accessible educational materials and animated videos were aimed to address these gaps. Moving forward, such communication efforts should be prioritized and integrated into project timelines from the beginning.

A key innovation within the LL framework was the use of personas to guide engagement and tool development. These personas provided a nuanced understanding of community motivations and barriers, ensuring that ACCEPT solutions were designed with end-users in mind. However, the process revealed certain limitations, particularly regarding inclusivity. The gender imbalance in survey respondents, for instance, underscored the need for more proactive efforts to engage underrepresented groups.

The user testing of digital tools within the LL framework offered valuable insights into their usability and impact. While the iterative testing process ensured that community feedback was incorporated into tool development, persistent challenges—such as interface complexity and lack of real-time data—revealed a disconnect between user expectations and the delivered solutions. Regional disparities in satisfaction further emphasized the need for localized customization. These findings reinforce the importance of prioritizing simplicity, clarity, and intuitive design in future iterations of digital tools.

One of the most profound lessons of the ACCEPT project was the importance of trust-building in community engagement. Trust—or the lack thereof—emerged as a decisive factor influencing the success of pilot activities. Communities with pre-existing levels of trust in local institutions and project leaders were more receptive to participation, while those with a history of mistrust required extensive effort to overcome scepticism. Trust-building measures, such as consistent communication, transparency in decision-making, and visible impacts, should therefore be central to any engagement strategy.

The project also highlighted the critical role of inclusivity in fostering meaningful participation. Engagement strategies must account for the diverse needs, motivations, and barriers of all community members, not just the most active or vocal participants. For example, gender-specific preferences for smart home automation, as observed during site visits, suggest that one-size-fits-all approaches are unlikely to succeed. Future projects must adopt more granular strategies to address these differences, ensuring that all stakeholders feel represented and valued.

In evaluating the Living Lab approach, while it provides a robust framework for co-creation and innovation, its success depends heavily on the context in which it is implemented. The methodology's strength lies in its flexibility and focus on user involvement, but its effectiveness can be undermined by insufficient capacity-building, communication gaps, or a failure to address deep-seated mistrust.

Moving forward, several recommendations can be drawn from the ACCEPT project. First, capacity-building efforts should be intensified at the project's inception to ensure all stakeholders are prepared to engage effectively. This includes providing training on digital tools, clarifying technical concepts, and fostering a shared understanding of project goals. Second, communication strategies must be prioritized, with a focus on creating accessible, localized materials that demystify complex topics and highlight the tangible benefits of participation. Third, digital tools should be designed with usability at their core. Iterative testing must continue to play a central role, but greater attention should be paid to aligning tool features with user expectations. Fourth, inclusivity should be embedded in all aspects of project planning and implementation. This requires proactive efforts to engage underrepresented groups, address diverse preferences, and ensure that all voices are heard.

Finally, trust-building must be recognized as a foundational element of community engagement. Consistent, transparent communication, coupled with visible impacts and the involvement of trusted local actors, can help overcome scepticism and foster long-term relationships.

In conclusion, the ACCEPT project's Living Lab approach has provided a rich repository of lessons and best practices for community engagement in energy transitions. By addressing the identified challenges and building on the

project's successes, future initiatives can leverage this methodology to create more inclusive, impactful, and sustainable energy communities. The key lies in balancing flexibility with structure, innovation with practicality, and inclusivity with targeted action, ensuring that the benefits of energy projects are accessible to all.

6. References

- Archibald, M. M., Wittmeier, K., Gale, M., Ricci, M. F., Russell, K., & Woodgate, R. L. (2021). Living labs for patient engagement and knowledge exchange: an exploratory sequential mixed methods study to develop a living lab in paediatric rehabilitation. *BMJ Open*, 11(5), e041530. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-041530>
- Compagnucci, L., Spigarelli, F., Coelho, J., & Duarte, C. (2021). Living labs and user engagement for innovation and sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125721. European Network of Living Labs. (n.d.). About us. <https://enoll.org/about-us/>
- Cooper, A. (1999). *The inmates are running the asylum* (pp. 17-17). Vieweg+ Teubner Verlag.
- Fotis, T., Kioskli, K., Sundaralingam, A., Fasihi, A., & Mouratidis, H. (2023). Co-creation in a digital health living lab: a case study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.892930>
- Hossain, M., Leminen, S., & Westerlund, M. (2019). A systematic review of living lab literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 213, 976-988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.257>
- King, C., & Cruickshank, M. (2012). Building capacity to engage: community engagement or government engagement? *Community Development Journal*, 47 (1), 5–28. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsq018>
- Lennon, B., Dunphy, N. P., Quinlivan, L., Velasco-Herrejón, P., Gaffney, C., & Tanulku, B. (2021). Report on existing European energy communities and success factors. Deliverable 3.6 of the ACCEPT H2020 project.
- Lupp, G., Zingraff-Hamed, A., Huang, J., Oen, A., & Pauleit, S. (2020). Living labs—a concept for co-designing nature-based solutions. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 188. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010188>
- Michie, S., Van Stralen, M. M., & West, R. (2011). The behaviour change wheel: a new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions. *Implementation science*, 6, 1-12.
- MacQueen, K. M., McLellan, E., Metzger, D. S. K. S., Strauss, R. P., Scotti, R., Blanchard, L., & Trotter II, R. T. (2001). What Is Community? An Evidence-Based Definition for Participatory Public Health. *American Journal of Public Health*, 91, 1929–1938. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.91.12.1929>
- Mcmillan, D. W., & Chavis, D. M. (1986). Sense of Community: A Definition and Theory. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 14 (1) 6-23.
- Potters, J., Collins, K., Schoorlemmer, H., Stræte, E. P., Kılıs, E., Lane, A., & Leloup, H. (2022). Living labs as an approach to strengthen agricultural knowledge and innovation systems. *EuroChoices*, 21(1), 23-29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-692x.12342>
- Roberts, J., Frieden, D., & D'Herbemont, S. (2019). Energy Community Definitions. In *COMPILE H2020* project (Issue May). <https://www.compile-project.eu/>
- Stroud, J. T., Bush, M. R., Ladd, M. C., Nowicki, R. J., Shantz, A. A., & Sweatman, J. (2015). Is a community still a community? Reviewing definitions of key terms in community ecology. *Ecology and Evolution*, 5 (21), 4757–4765. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1651>
- Torres, E. N. (2020). Online-to-Offline Interactions and Online Community Life Cycles: A Longitudinal Study of Shared Leisure Activities. *Leisure Sciences*, 42 (1), 32–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490400.2017.1392913>
- Tukiainen, T., Leminen, S., & Westerlund, M. (2015). Cities as collaborative innovation platforms. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 5(10), 16-23. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/933>
- Tuladhar, P. (2020). Gender and energy for space heating and cooling. *Journal of the Institute of Engineering*, 15(3), 368-374. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jie.v15i3.32224>

Watson, D. (2008), The university in the modern world: Ten lessons of civic and community engagement. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 3 (1) <https://doi.org/10.1177/17461979070867>

Westerlund, M., Leminen, S., & Rajahonka, M. (2018). A topic modelling analysis of living labs research. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 8(7), 40-51. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1170>

7. Appendices

7.1. Appendix A: System Usability Scale

System Usability Scale (SUS) (5 min)

Ask the participant to provide a response on a scale of 1 – 5.

1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree.

Type the number of their response next to each question.

- I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
- I found the system unnecessarily complex.
- I thought the system was easy to use.
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
- I found the various functions in this system were well integrated
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly
- I found the system very cumbersome to use.
- I felt very confident using the system.
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.